

wherein the dimeric structure of copper acetate has been destroyed⁹.

References

1. M. BIAGIACINGI, A. CHIERSIVILLA, A. G. MANFREDOTTI and C. GUASTINI, *Cryst. Struct. Commun.*, 1972, 1, 363.
2. H. J. KRENTZIEN, M. J. CLARKE and H. TAUBE, *Bio. Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, 4, 143.
3. R. L. DUTTA and DHURUBANANDA DE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 76.
4. H. SHIRAI, Y. INAKI and K. TAKEMOTO, *Makromol. Chem.*, 1974, 175, 2047.
5. N. C. LI, L. JOHNSON and J. SHOOLERY, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, 65, 1902.
6. N. C. LI, R. L. SCRUGGS and E. D. BECKER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 4650.
7. P. TANG and N. C. LI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 1293.
8. K. S. BOSE and C. C. PATEL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, 32, 1141.

Mixed-ligand Complexes of Diamine (salicylato) Cu(II) and Diamine(salicylato) Ni(II) with 2-hydroxyacetophenone or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde

B.R. SINGHVI, D.C. SEHGAL and R.K. MEHTA

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur,
Jodhpur (INDIA)

Manuscript received on 7 May 1977, revised 2 September 1977,
accepted 7 December 1977

A survey of the literature¹⁻³ has revealed that no work has been done on the mixed-ligand complexes of diamine(salicylato) Cu(II) and diamine (salicylato) Ni(II) with 2-hydroxyacetophenone or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde. The present note deals with the mixed-ligand (Schiff base) complexes, synthesised by the interaction of 2-hydroxyacetophenone or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde with the mixed complexes of the type [ML-1, 3 diaminopropane], where LH_2 = salicylic acid. The resulting mixed-ligand complexes retain (L^{-2}) in their structure while the -OH groups of the Schiff base N-N'-propylene bis(α -methyl-2-hydroxybenzylidene imino) or N-N'-propylene bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde imino) remain unco-ordinated.

The metal salicylates were treated with ethylene diamine or propylene diamine and the diamine (salicylato) Cu(II) and diamine(salicylato) Ni(II) obtained by the following two procedures :

(1) To a mixture of equimolar (1 M) aqueous solution of nickel chloride and salicylic acid in the ratio of 1 : 2, an aqueous solution of 1, 3-diamino propane (1 M) was added till the pH was ~6. After 40-45 minutes a greenish-blue precipitate was

obtained. It was filtered, washed, dried, weighed and analysed. (2) Alternatively bis or tris-(1, 3-diamino propane) nickel(II) chloride (0.5 g) was dissolved in the minimum quantity of water and to it an aqueous solution of salicylic acid (1 M) was added till pH 6 was attained. After 40 minutes or so a greenish-blue compound obtained, was filtered, washed, dried, weighed and analysed. These compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and metal analysis and based on these data their composition (Fig. 1) may be expressed by [MLA] $2H_2O$, where M = Cu(II) or Ni(II), LH_2 = salicylic acid and A = ethylenediamine or propylene diamine.

Fig. 1. Mixed-ligand Complexes of Diamine (Salicylato) M(II) with 2-Hydroxyacetophenone.

The analysis of the diamine(salicylato) metal(II) indicate them to be the mixed complexes. The water molecules associated with them are lost at 130° suggesting them to be either co-ordinated or water of crystallisation.

These mixed complexes were treated with 2-hydroxyacetophenone or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde so that the two -NH₂ groups of the co-ordinated diamine molecule undergo condensation as described below.

A requisite quantity (0.5 g) of the mixed complex was refluxed with 10.0 ml of 2-hydroxyacetophenone or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde on a water-bath for 3 hours. The solution was concentrated and the mixed-ligand complex was rendered insoluble by adding an excess of ether in which the unreacted 2-hydroxyacetophenone or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde dissolved. The mixed-ligand complex was recrystallised from chloroform. Elemental analysis and molecular weight determinations give the formula [ML-SB] for these compounds, where SB stands for N-N' propylene bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene) or N-N' propylene bis(α -methyl-2-hydroxy benzylidene).

The magnetic susceptibility measurements of the mixed-ligand complexes (Fig. 1) suggest the diamagnetic nature of the Ni(II)-complexes⁴ and paramagnetic nature to the extent of one unpaired electron for the Cu(II)-complexes⁵ (1.82 B. M.) at room temperature.

The electronic absorption spectra of the mixed complexes in water and mixed-ligand complexes in chloroform gave absorption peaks in the range of 300-950 nm.

The mixed-ligand copper(II) complexes in chloroform gave a broad absorption band at 500 nm suggesting their square-planar geometry. The mixed-ligand nickel(II) complexes gave two bands at ~420 nm and 510 nm and in no case absorption bands beyond 600 nm were observed which indicate the square-planar geometry of the complexes.

The negligibly small values ($\Delta M = 5.0 - 7.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$) of molar-conductance of the mixed-ligand complexes in chloroform suggest them to be neutral in nature. The I.R. spectra indicate a broad band in the range $3600-3200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting that the $-\text{OH}$ groups are unco-ordinated.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to CSIR, New Delhi for the award of fellowship to one of them (BRS).

References

1. UMA DORASWAMY and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 1665
2. B. T. THAKKER and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 615.
3. R. L. DUTTA and ANJANA BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 239.
4. R. W. ASMUSSEN, A. JENSEN and H. SALING, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1955, **9**, 1391.
5. E. N. BAKER, D. HALL and T. N. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 680.

Viscosity of NaCl, NaBr and NaNO₃ in Dioxane-Water Mixtures at Different Temperatures

P. P. MISRA, N. C. DAS and P. B. DAS

Department of Chemistry, S.C.S. College, Puri

Manuscript received 4 September 1976, revised 25 March 1977, accepted 24 November 1977

THE variation of viscosity with temperature and solvent compositions has been employed to study the ion-solvent interaction by many workers¹, both

in aqueous and non-aqueous solutions. In the present communication an attempt has been made to deal with the ion-solvent interaction of NaCl, NaBr and NaNO₃ in dioxane-water mixtures of varying compositions to see the effect of temperature and hydrogen bonding on the B-coefficient of the viscosity equation. The activation energy and the entropy of activation of the viscous flow of these solutions have also been calculated for interpreting the influence of strong electrolytes upon the viscosity of the solvent as a rate process.

All the salts used were of E. Merck 'extra pure varieties'. The samples were recrystallised, dried at 180° and kept in vacuum. Preparation of the solvent, solutions and procedure for measurement were the same as described earlier².

The Jones-Dole equation¹ has been found to be adequate as the plot of $\eta_r - 1/C^{1/2}$ vs $C^{1/2}$ is found to be linear. This is in contrary to that of the results of P. K. Das³ who has used an empirical equation: $\eta_r = 1 + AC^{1/2} + BC^x$, where 'x' is an empirical constant without any physical significance. The constant B of the Jones-Dole equation which is regarded as a measure of the ion-solvent interaction could be calculated, from the slope of the above plot, are tabulated in Table 1. The B value increases in case of NaCl and NaNO₃ with increase in temperature whereas it is irregular in case of NaBr. The plot of 'B' vs 't' is linear for NaCl and NaNO₃ whereas it is a curve for NaBr.

Nightingale⁴ has suggested the B value as a measure of ion-dipole interaction. Dioxane is more or less a non-hydrogen bonded solvent. So the ion-dipole interaction energy in the absence of any hydrogen bond energy would be appreciable and the attachment of the solvent molecules to the ions may not be loose and hence no structure formation would occur in the solvents around the ion⁵. The net result will be stronger solvation and more ion-solvent interaction.

Proceeding in the similar manner as that of Nightingale⁵ et al, the energy of activation ΔE , free

TABLE—1

Temp. in °C.	B/l. mol ⁻¹								
	10% D	20% D NaCl	30% D	10% D	20% D NaBr	30% D	10% D	20% D NaNO ₃	30% D
30	0.091	0.1002	0.1554	0.0971	0.1200	0.1510	0.071	0.0955	0.1302
35	0.091	0.1122	0.1662	0.1150	0.1240	0.1700	0.085	0.01085	0.1420
40	0.1400	0.1500	0.2000	0.0661	0.1122	0.1445	0.1020	0.1148	0.1530
45	0.1500	0.1620	0.2200	0.0648	0.1080	0.1120	0.1120	0.1250	0.1600

TABLE—2

Solvent	10% D			20% D			30% D		
	ΔE in K cal	ΔF in K cal	ΔS in E.U.	ΔE in K cal	ΔF in K cal	ΔS in E.U.	ΔE in K cal	ΔF in K cal	ΔS in E.U.
NaCl	4.084	2.290	5.82	4.158	2.491	5.41	4.022	2.530	6.63
NaBr	4.221	2.308	5.97	4.358	2.571	5.70	4.292	2.710	6.79
NaNO ₃	3.852	2.260	5.62	4.048	2.361	5.61	3.894	2.457	6.49
	3.899	2.263	5.70	4.086	2.371	5.23	3.911	2.506	6.51